

THE SIGNIFICANCE AND POTENTIAL OF BRONCHOSCOPY IN DIAGNOSING CONGENITAL BRONCHIAL ANOMALIES

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Introduction

Diseases associated with congenital anomalies of the airways during the neonatal and infant periods represent life-threatening conditions. These conditions not only require urgent resuscitation measures but also demand early and accurate diagnosis, as they often manifest with rare and complex clinical presentations. Congenital bronchial anomalies—such as bronchomalacia, bronchial stenosis, bronchogenic cysts, and bronchial atresia—are structural defects occurring at the bronchial level. These anomalies often lead to partial or complete obstruction of the airways due to cystic masses or dynamic collapse, hindering normal airflow.

Radiological methods like X-ray or CT scans often fail to adequately detect these anomalies in early infancy. Therefore, bronchoscopy—allowing for direct visualization of the airways and enabling tissue biopsy—is considered the most effective diagnostic method in such cases.

Relevance of the problem

Congenital bronchial anomalies occur in approximately 1–2 out of every 10,000 live births. Delayed diagnosis may result in recurrent respiratory infections, pneumonia, the need for mechanical ventilation, and even perinatal death. Rapid and accurate diagnosis through effective methods is essential. Bronchoscopy is not only a diagnostic tool but also offers therapeutic opportunities. International studies have shown that early bronchoscopy helps reduce the preoperative period, limits complications, and decreases reliance on antibiotics.

Objective of the study

To evaluate the diagnostic effectiveness and clinical potential of bronchoscopy in identifying congenital bronchial anomalies in neonates and infants, as well as its role in treatment planning.

Materials and methods

This study included 26 pediatric patients treated in the pediatric department from 2021 to 2024, who presented with symptoms suggestive of bronchial pathology. The patients ranged from 3 days to 12 months old. All underwent primary imaging via CT and chest radiography, followed by flexible bronchoscopy.

Bronchoscopic procedures were performed using pediatric flexible bronchoscopes manufactured by Pentax and Olympus. Anesthesia was administered in accordance with pediatric safety guidelines.

Results and discussion

Among the 26 infants examined: 8 cases of bronchomalacia were identified, mostly involving the central bronchi. These cases presented with noisy breathing and signs of retraction. 6 cases of bronchogenic cysts were visualized as external compressions on bronchoscopy. In some cases, biopsies were obtained. 4 cases of bronchial atresia were confirmed. While CT scans showed signs of complete obstruction, bronchoscopy allowed precise localization of the blockage. 3 cases of bronchial stenosis were detected. These children exhibited persistent hypoxia and recurrent pneumonia due to narrowed airways. 5 cases presented with various congenital obstructions and abnormal bronchial wall formations.

Bronchoscopy facilitated additional interventions in multiple cases:

Biopsies in 12 patients

Aspiration of secretions in 5 patients

Direct bronchial therapeutic procedures in 4 patients

Conclusion

Bronchoscopy is a highly effective and reliable diagnostic method for detecting congenital bronchial anomalies. It enables the evaluation of both morphological changes and functional impact. Bronchoscopy is particularly recommended in cases of unexplained pneumonia, recurrent respiratory symptoms, or dependency on mechanical ventilation. Combined with radiological methods, it plays a crucial role in comprehensive diagnosis and treatment planning.

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